

ACCESSIBILITY OF AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION SERVICES BY FARMERS: IMPLICATIONS FOR FOOD SECURITY IN NORTH WEST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the accessibility of extension services among farmers and its implications for food security in Nigeria. A Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to sample 378 respondents from Kaduna and Kano States. Descriptive (percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) and Binomial test) were used to analyse data of the study. Findings revealed that 75.40% of farmers had access to extension services and key factors influencing access, include socio-economic characteristics (mean = 3.08), availability of extension agents (mean = 3.03), membership in farm-based organizations (mean = 3.04), financial resources (mean = 2.97), training (mean = 2.94), and access to ICTs (mean = 2.94). The results showed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.7452$) between farmers' access to extension services and farm productivity, with statistical significance at the 1% level. The study also confirmed a significant difference in food security levels between farmers with access to extension services and those without, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. However, major challenges hindering effective extension service delivery included inadequate funding (92.86%), poor logistics (91.01%), an unfavorable extension agent-to-farmer ratio (88.89%), and limited training for both farmers and extension agents. Political interference and lack of government commitment (54.76%) further constrained service efficiency. There is a need for increased government and private sector investment in extension services, improved infrastructure, and enhanced training programs for extension personnel.

Keywords: Farm productivity, food security, accessibility, adoption, extension workers, farm practices

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture remains a cornerstone of Nigeria's economy, playing a crucial role in employment, food security, and economic growth (Nwogwugwu *et al.*, 2023). Touch *et al.* (2024) stated that despite its importance, the sector continues to grapple with numerous challenges, including low productivity, limited access to modern

farming techniques, climate change, and insufficient support services. Among the key factors influencing agricultural development and food security is the availability of agricultural extension services for farmers (Masanja *et al.*, 2023). Masanja *et al.* (2023) stressed that these services are essential for disseminating knowledge, skills, and improved farming

methods, helping farmers enhance productivity and sustain food production. It is important to note that in most developing countries like Nigeria, where agriculture serves as a primary livelihood for many households, the accessibility and effectiveness of extension services have a direct impact on food security (Akpabio *et al.*, 2024). Agricultural extension services are essential for improving farmers' productivity by facilitating the transfer of research-based knowledge, innovative farming techniques, and best agricultural practices from experts to farmers (Akpabio *et al.*, 2024). The services actually serve to bridge the gap between scientific advancements and practical on-farm applications, equipping farmers with essential information on improved seeds, soil fertility management, pest control, post-harvest handling, and climate-smart agriculture (Mungai *et al.*, 2024). However, despite the significance of agricultural extension, many smallholder farmers in Nigeria, particularly in Kaduna and Kano States, struggle to access these services (Momodu *et al.*, 2024). Touch *et al.* (2024) thought that challenges such as inadequate extension personnel, poor funding, weak institutional frameworks, and infrastructural deficiencies hinder the effectiveness of extension programs, limiting farmers' ability to adopt improved agricultural practices. As a result, farmers struggle to implement improved agricultural practices, leading to reduced productivity, increased post-harvest losses, and heightened vulnerability to food insecurity. Tackling these challenges is essential to improving agricultural efficiency and ensuring long-term food sustainability in the region. The accessibility of agricultural extension services is closely linked to food security (Kauky, 2024). According to Otekinrin and Otekinrin (2021), food security is achieved when all individuals have consistent

physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food. Without adequate agricultural extension services, farmers lack the necessary knowledge and resources to enhance productivity, leading to food shortages, reduced incomes, and increased vulnerability to food insecurity (Ranjan *et al.*, 2024). Conversely, well-structured and widely accessible extension services empower farmers to embrace modern agricultural practices, boost crop yields, strengthen resilience to climate change, and contribute to both household and national food security (Mustapha *et al.*, 2024). This study broadly aims to assess the extent to which farmers in Kaduna and Kano State can access agricultural extension services and examine the implications for food security. Gaining insights into this study is essential for developing policies and interventions that promote agricultural productivity and food security in Kaduna and Kano States.

Hypotheses of the study (H₀):

Hoi: The level of accessibility of agricultural extension services does not significantly improve farm productivity in the study area.

Hoi: There is no significant difference in food security levels between farmers with access to extension services and those without.

METHODOLOGY The study was carried out in Kaduna and Kano States both of which are in North West geo-political zone of Nigeria.

Kaduna State Kaduna State is situated in the North-West geo-political zone of Nigeria, within the northern region. Geographically, it lies between Latitude 9°00' - 13° 49'N and Longitude 3°45' - 10° 20'E , spanning an expansive 46,053 km². This makes Kaduna

State the fourth largest in terms of land area among Nigeria's 36 states. The state capital, Kaduna city, is one of the 23 local government areas (LGAs) within the state (Okwuokenye and Petu-Ibikunle, 2021). Kaduna State is the third most populous state in Nigeria, with an estimated 9,032,200 residents as of 2022 (Kaduna State, Nigeria Population Statistics, 2022). Approximately 80% of the state's population relies on agriculture for their livelihood (Okwuokenye and Petu-Ibikunle, 2021). While Hausa is the predominant spoken language, English is the official language.

Kano State

Kano State, situated in the North-West geo-political zone of Nigeria, is located at coordinates 11.74710° N, 8.52470° E. The State comprises 44 Local Government Areas (LGAs), with Kano City as its capital. As of 2022, Kano State has an estimated population of 15,462,200, according to the National Population Commission (NPC, 2022), making it the most populous state in Nigeria. The state borders Katsina to the northwest, Jigawa to the northeast, Bauchi to the southeast, and Kaduna to the southwest. Kano State is home to several major ethnic groups, including Hausa, Fulani, Beriberi (Kanuri), Tuareg, Arab, and Nupe, with Hausa being the predominant language. Kano State is Nigeria's second-largest industrial hub, after Lagos. It boasts a diverse range of industries, including textiles, leather tanning, footwear, cosmetics, plastics, pharmaceuticals, ceramics, and furniture manufacturing. The state's economy is primarily agrarian, with approximately

70% of the population engaged in agricultural activities. Kano State is also endowed with an array of mineral resources, including cassiterite, copper, glass sand, lead/zinc, gemstones, pyrochlore, and tantalite. However, the state grapples with several challenges, such as inter-religious tensions, economic difficulties, and sporadic attacks by the extremist group Boko Haram.

Sampling procedure and sampling size of the study

Multi-stage random sampling method was used for selecting the respondents. It started with stage 1 which involved the random selection of the Kaduna and Kano States from the North-West geo-political. This was followed by stage 2, which involved random selection of 2 agricultural zones from each of the states, thus making it 4 that were used. Stage 3 involved the random selection of 2 LGAs from each of the agricultural zones, and this made it 8 in such that were used for the study. This was followed by the random selection of 2 towns/villages from each of the LGAs, thus making it 16 towns/villages that were used for the study (stage 4). Stage 5 involved the random selection of 25 farmers from each of the towns/villages and this resulted to a total of 400 farmers that were contacted for the study. They were administered the question instrument, and from those returned, 378 (94.5%) of them that were found suitable for analysis were used for the study. Table 1 provides details of the states, agricultural zones, LGAs, and towns/ villages used in the study.

Table 1: Showing states, agricultural zones, L GAs and villages/communities of the study

State	Agricultural zone	LGA	Village/community	No. of farmers
Kaduna	Kaduna Central	Birnin Gwari	Birnin Gwari	25
			Kwaga	25
		Chikun	Sabon-Tasha	25
			Kuriga	25
	Kaduna South	Kachia	Adage	25
			Badoko	25
		Kaura	Kaura	25
			K ukum	25
Kano	Kano Central	Nasar awa	Obi	25
			Lafia	25
		Kano Municipal	Sheshe	25
			Albasa	25
	Kano South	Tudun Wada	Dalawa	25
			Sumana	25
		Rano	Rano	25
			Dawaki	25
Total = 2	4 Agric.zone	8 LGAs	16 towns/villages	400 farmers

Validation of research instrument and source of data The research instrument was validated using the face content method, while reliability was determined through test-re-test method. It produced correlation coefficient of r-value of 0.71 which implies that the instrument was highly reliable. The study was carried out with the use of primary data. They were collected using structured questionnaire and interview schedule, which were administered to literate and illiterate farmers, respectively.

Data analytical technique

The study data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics involved the presentation of data in frequency tables, utilizing percentages, means, and standard deviations to assess the level of farmers' access to agricultural extension services. A four-point Likert scale was employed to evaluate the role of extension agents and

key factors influencing farmers' accessibility to extension services. The scale included the following response options: Strongly Agree (coded 4), Agree (coded 3), Disagree (coded 2), and Strongly Disagree (coded 1). A weighted mean score of 2.50 or higher was considered indicative of the role of extension agents and key influencing factors, while values below 2.50 were regarded as less significant. The weighted mean score of 2.50 was derived using the formula: $(4 + 3 + 2 + 1) / 4 = 2.50$. The impacts of farmers' access to extension services on food security, as well as the challenges hindering effective extension service delivery, were analyzed using a four-point scale and presented in percentages. Regarding the impact of extension service accessibility on food security, the scale ranged from insignificant impact (rank 1), minor impact (rank 2), moderate impact (rank 3), and major impact (rank 4). Any factor identified by at least 50% of the respondents as an impact of extension service accessibility was considered a major impact on food security.

Conversely, if fewer than 50% of respondents identified a factor as an impact, it was not considered a major impact. Similarly, for challenges hindering effective extension service delivery, the scale ranged from insignificant challenge (rank 1), minor challenge (rank 2), moderate challenge (rank 3), and major challenge (rank 4). Any challenge recognized by 50% or more of the respondents was classified as a major challenge to effective extension service delivery. However, if the responses were less than 50%, the challenge was not deemed significant. Hypothesis one was analyzed using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r), which measures the linear relationship between farmers' level of access to extension services (X) and farm

productivity (Y). The correlation coefficient ranges from -1 to +1, where: +1 indicates a perfect positive relationship, meaning an increase in level of farmers' access to extension services (X) corresponds to an increase in farm productivity (Y). On the other hand, -1 indicates a perfect inverse relationship, meaning an increase in level of farmers' access to extension services (X) leads to a decrease in farm productivity (Y). Interpreting further, 0 indicates no correlation, meaning there is no relationship between level of farmers' access to extension services and farm productivity. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient is expressed as follows

$$r = \frac{n \sum XY - (\sum X) (\sum Y)}{(\sqrt{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X^2)}) (n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y^2))} \text{----- (eq. 1)}$$

Decision Rule: A reliable decision is made by accepting the alternative hypothesis and rejecting the null hypothesis when the parameter estimate is statistically significant. This occurs when the standard error is less than half the value of the parameter estimate.

compare the number of farmers with access to extension services against those without access and assess its impact on food security levels. A two-tailed binomial test was conducted to determine the statistical significance of the difference in proportions between these two groups. The binomial distribution formula is presented below:

Hypothesis 2 was analyzed using the Binomial Test, which was employed to
 $b(x;n,p) = nC_x * p^x * (1-p)^{n-x}$ ----- (eq. 2) where b
 = binomial probability; x = total number of successes (access or no access to extension

services)

p = probability of success on an individual trial;
 n = number of trials.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of farmers' access to extension services Table 2 presents the level of farmers' access to agricultural extension services. The results indicate that a significant proportion (44.44%) of respondents had moderate access to extension services. Overall, approximately 86.24% of farmers had a reasonable level of accessibility to agricultural extension services. This suggests that with such access, farmers are more likely to be exposed to new innovations, technologies, and up-to-date

agricultural information, which can enhance food security both at the individual and national levels. This finding aligns with the conclusion of Ranjan *et al.* (2024), who emphasized that agricultural extension services are essential for achieving food security. Their study highlighted that extension services play a critical role in enhancing agricultural productivity, promoting sustainable farming practices, and improving farmers' livelihoods, all of which collectively contribute to food security at both individual and national levels.

Table 2: Level of farmers' access to agricultural extension services

Level of farmers' access to extension services	Frequency	Percentage	Mode
-Highly accessible	67	17.73	
-Moderately accessible	168	44.44	
-Partially accessible	91	24.07	
- Minimally accessible	29	7.67	
-Inaccessible	23	6.09	
Total	378	100.00	Moderately accessible

Source: Field survey, 2024

Factors influencing farmers' accessibility to extension services The results in Table 3 identify key factors influencing farmers' access to extension services, including: farmers' socio-economic characteristics (mean = 3.08), availability of extension agents (mean = 3.03), membership in farm-based organizations (mean = 3.04), availability of funds and other farm resources (mean = 2.97), training for capacity building (mean = 2.94) and access to Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) (mean = 2.94). These factors were ranked from 1st to 5th based on their influence on farmers' accessibility to extension services. Other influencing factors included the use of mobile apps and online platforms (mean = 2.93), good road network and

transportation system (mean = 2.86), distance of extension agents and their centers from farmers (mean = 2.79), farmers' social status (mean = 2.63), and trust and credibility (mean = 2.52). These factors were ranked 7th to 11th in their impact on farmers' accessibility to extension services. The results suggest that multiple factors play a role in determining farmers' access to extension services. The findings on farmers' socio-economic factors as a key influencer of accessibility to extension services align with the study by Ndanitsa *et al.* (2021), which reported that farmers with higher education levels, larger farm sizes, and higher income levels are more likely to have greater access to extension services. Additionally, Ndanitsa *et al.* (2021) supported the role of

membership in farm-based organizations, emphasizing that such memberships facilitate knowledge sharing and networking, thereby improving access to extension agents and agricultural information. Similarly, Declaro-Ruedas (2019) affirmed that capacity building through training is a crucial factor, as it empowers farmers with essential knowledge and innovations, enhancing their ability to adopt improved agricultural practices. The availability of extension workers aligns with the findings of Kristin *et al.* (2019), who emphasized that reducing the extension worker-to-farmer ratio enhances farmers' access to extension services. In a like manner, the findings of Ozioko *et al.* (2022) support the role of funding and resource availability as a key factor in improving farmers' access to extension services. They highlighted that providing financial support and incentives serves as an effective strategy to encourage farmers to engage with extension services. The findings on farmers' access to ICTs and the use of mobile apps are supported by Olorunfemi *et al.* (2020), who emphasized

that effective management of ICT tools and mobile applications for extension services can significantly enhance farmers' access to vital agricultural information. Additionally, the issue of distance between extension agents, extension centers, and farmers aligns with the findings of Owusu *et al.* (2020). They emphasized the need to maintain well-functioning extension centres and agents to foster a strong connection and efficient flow of information between farmers and extension services. Furthermore, farmers' trust in extension workers and the services they provide was identified as a key influencing factor, aligning with the findings of Kavakebi *et al.* (2023). Their study highlighted that the level of trust farmers place in extension agents directly affects their access to and adoption of agricultural information. Additionally, farmers with higher social status may have greater access to extension services, as they are more likely to possess the necessary resources required by extension agents, facilitating better engagement and support.

Table 3: Factors influencing farmers' accessibility to extension services

Influencing factors	Mean	Standard Dev.	Rank
-Socio-economic factors of the farmer	3.08*	0.73	1 st
-Availability of extension agent	3.03*	0.61	2 nd
-Membership of farm-based organizations	3.04*	0.76	3 rd
-Availability of funds and other farm resources	2.97*	0.58	4 th
-Training of farmers on capacity building	2.94*	0.53	5 th
-Access to Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs)	2.94*	0.75	5 th
-Use of mobile apps and on-line platforms	2.93*	0.79	7 th
-Good road network and transportation system	2.86*	0.65	8 th
-Distance of extension centres and agents from the farmers	2.79*	0.57	9 th
-Farmers social status	2.63*	0.49	10 th
-Trust and credibility	2.52*	0.50	11 th
-Unconducive weather condition	2.42	0.58	12 th
-Farmers attitude towards new farm practices	2.42	0.63	13 th
-Traditional / cultural beliefs	2.31	0.61	14 th

Agreed (mean ≥ 2.50);

Source: Field survey, 2024

The role of extension agents to farmers

The roles performed by extension agents in supporting farmers are presented in Table 4, highlighting their diverse responsibilities. The findings indicate that the primary role of extension agents is the provision of agricultural information (mean = 2.93). This is followed by: providing technical advice (mean = 2.91), offering advisory services (mean = 2.90), training farmers in farm skills (mean = 2.85), demonstrating proper input use (mean = 2.84) and facilitating access to inputs and credit (mean = 2.66). These roles collectively enhance farmers' knowledge, productivity, and overall agricultural development. The results indicate that extension agents play multiple essential roles in supporting farmers, emphasizing their significance in

enhancing farm productivity, income generation, and national food security. The findings on the provision of agricultural information, technical advice on farm practices, off-farm advisory services, farmer training, and access to inputs and credit align with the study by Ranjan *et al.* (2024). Their research highlighted that agricultural extension services are vital for disseminating knowledge and technologies, providing crucial support to farmers in these areas. Additionally, the role of demonstration on input use is supported by Okwuokenye (2022), who noted that this service is one of the key benefits gained by community-based organization farmers through participation in extension agent training programmes.

Table 4: The role of extension agents to farmers

Role of extension agents	Mean	Standard Dev.	Rank
-Providing agricultural information	2.93*	0.66	1 st
-Provision of technical advice on farm practices	2.91*	0.58	2 nd
-Provision of off-farm advisory services	2.90*	0.51	3 rd
-Training of farmers on farming skills	2.85*	0.66	4 th
-Demonstration on input use	2.84*	0.76	5 th
-Providing access to inputs and credit	2.66*	0.71	6 th
-Visiting farmers regularly	2.32	0.60	7 th
-Supplies of necessary farm inputs	2.21	0.51	8 th

Agreed (mean ≥ 2.50);

Source: Field survey, 2024

Impact of extension service accessibility by farmers on food security Farmers' access to extension services has equipped them with agricultural education, essential resources, and support, leading to significant improvements in food security at household, community, and national levels (see Table 5 for details). The findings indicate that the key benefits of these services include year-round food availability (76.98%), increased income from agricultural activities (72.49%),

higher crop yields (66.40%), enhanced adoption of new technologies and best practices (61.64%), and reduced post-harvest losses (57.94%). Additional benefits of farmers' access to extension services include improved adaptation to climate change (55.82%), consumption of nutritionally adequate food (53.70%), access to food that helps reduce the risk of diet-related diseases (50.79%), and increased participation in cooperative groups and farm-based organizations

(50.26%). These findings suggest that access to extension services has positively influenced farmers' productivity, income, and food security. The improvements in food availability, crop yield, nutritional adequacy, and income align with the findings of Ranjan et al. (2024), who asserted that exposure to modern agricultural practices through extension services leads to these positive outcomes for farmers. The findings on the provision of agricultural information, particularly regarding new farming techniques and extension services for post-harvest handling (reducing wastage), align with the research of Loki and Mdoda (2023). They emphasized that access to agricultural information on innovative technologies enhances production, increases income, and improves the standard of living among farming communities. Similarly, Dansa-Abbeam *et al.* (2018) supported the results, highlighting that agricultural information not only boosts farm productivity and income but also accelerates the adoption rate of improved farming practices, ultimately contributing to a better quality of life for farmers.

Table 5: Impacts of farmers' access to extension services on food security

Effects of farmers access to extension services	Insignificant impact	Minor impact	Moderate impact	Major impact	Remark
-Availability of food throughout the year	6 (1.59%)	10 (2.65%)	71 (18.78%)	291 (76.98%)	Agreed
- Increased income from Agriculture	14 (3.70%)	22 (5.82%)	68 (17.99%)	274 (72.49%)	Agreed
-Increased crop yield	21 (5.56%)	43 (11.38%)	63 (16.67%)	251 (66.40%)	Agreed
-Improved adoption of new technologies and best practices	28 (7.41%)	48 (12.70%)	69 (18.25%)	233 (61.64%)	Agreed
-Reduction in post-harvest losses	25 (6.61%)	61 (16.14%)	73 (19.31%)	219 (57.94%)	Agreed
-Equipped with agricultural information on new farm technology	36 (9.52%)	52 (13.76%)	79 (20.90%)	211 (55.82%)	Agreed
-Consuming food that meets the requirements of the body	49 (12.96%)	41 (10.85%)	85 (22.48%)	203 (53.70%)	Agreed
-Provision and consumption of food that helps to reduce the risk of diet-related diseases	36 (9.52%)	49 (12.96%)	101 (26.72%)	192 (50.79%)	Agreed
-Increased association with cooperative groups and farm-based organization	38 (10.05%)	51 (13.49%)	99 (26.19%)	190 (50.26%)	Agreed
-Improved agri-business activities and marketing activities of farm products	34 (8.99%)	85 (22.49%)	92 (24.34%)	167 (44.18%)	Disagreed
-Improved farmers relevance in his/her community	101 (26.72%)	122 (32.28%)	74 (19.58%)	81 (21.43%)	Disagreed

Source: Field survey, 2024

Major impact= 50% and above

Factors limiting farmers access to extension services Effective agricultural extension service delivery is crucial for improving food security and rural development. However, the effectiveness of farmers access to extension services were agreed to have been constraint by several factors as shown in Table 6. The primary challenges identified were inadequate funding (92.86%) and poor logistical support (91.01%), indicating that agricultural extension services in the area suffer from insufficient financial resources and limited transportation for extension workers. This aligns with the findings of Odoh *et al.* (2023), who reported that inadequate funding and poor transportation remain significant constraints to the effective delivery of agricultural extension services to farmers. Additional challenges include an unfavorable extension-farmer ratio (88.89%), insufficient skilled manpower due to inadequate training (88.89%), poor infrastructure (83.07%), and low educational levels among farmers (80.69%). These findings suggest the need for more extension agents to bridge the existing gap and effectively reach a larger farming population. The transportation difficulties further hinder agents' ability to access remote farming communities for information dissemination. Additionally, the low literacy levels among farmers may limit their ability to comprehend and implement improved agricultural practices, while inadequate training for extension agents could result in a lack of the necessary expertise to effectively transfer knowledge to farmers. These findings align with the study by Bashir *et al.* (2022), which identified a poor extension agent-farmer ratio, inadequate

transportation for extension personnel, low farmer literacy levels, and insufficient training as key barriers to farmers' access to extension services. Additional constraints include the low adoption of recommended extension practices (76.46%) and limited financial resources among farmers (76.19%), which hinder their ability to embrace modern agricultural techniques. Since most farmers operate on a small scale with restricted resources, this significantly affects their adoption of improved farming methods, a challenge also highlighted by Illiyasu *et al.* (2023). Furthermore, poor attitudes among extension agents (70.63%) and inadequate motivation for extension staff (68.52%) were noted as additional barriers. The lack of motivation for extension personnel may contribute to their ineffective service delivery, further limiting farmers' access to critical agricultural support. These findings are consistent with Ojo *et al.* (2024), who identified inadequate funding and the unfavorable attitudes of extension workers as key barriers to farmers' access to extension services. Additionally, political interference and a lack of government commitment (54.76%) were noted as significant challenges, potentially disrupting the effective delivery of extension services. Lai-Solarin *et al.* (2024) further support this, highlighting that such issues lead to a fragmented approach to service delivery, with overlapping responsibilities among different levels of government agencies.

Table 6: Factors limiting farmers' access to extension services

Limiting factors to farmers' access to extension services	Insignificant challenge (%)	Minor challenge (%)	Moderate challenge (%)	Major challenge (%)	Remark	
-Inadequate funding	0 (0%)	4 (1.05%)	23 (6.09%)	351 (92.86%)	Agreed	
-Poor logistic support	5 (1.32%)	5 (1.32%)	29 (7.67%)	344 (91.01%)	Agreed	
- Low number of extension-farmer ratio		16 (4.23 %)	21 (5.56%) 25 (6.61%)	336 (88.89%)	Agreed	
-Insufficient skilled manpower due to lack of training	6 (1.59%)	11 (2.91%)		336 (88.89%)	Agreed	
- Poor infrastructure	17 (4.50%)	31 (8.20 %)	16 (4.23 %)	314 (83.07%)	Agreed	
-Low educational level of the farmers	14 (3.70%)	28 (1.41%)	28 (8.20%)	31 (8.20%)	305 (80.69%)	Agreed
-Low adoption of extension recommended practices	24 (6.35%) 23 (6.03%)	32 (8.47%)	33 (8.73%)	289 (76.46%)	Agreed	
- Poor/low farmers income/resources		32 (8.47 %)	42 (11.11 %)	288 (76.19%)	Agreed	
- Poor attitude of the extension agents	36 (9.52%)	47 (12.43%)	28 (7.41 %)	267 (70.63%)	Agreed	
-Inadequate motivation for extension staff	31 (8.20%)	39 (10.32%)	49 (12.96%)	259 (68.52%)	Agreed	
-Political interference and lack of government concern	75 (19.84%)	32 (8.47%)	64 (16.93%)	207 (54.76%)	Agreed	
-Custom and tradition of the farmers	101 (26.72%)	91 (24.07%)	73 (19.31%)	113 (29.89%)	Disagreed	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Major factor limiting farmers access to extension services = 50% and above

Relationship between accessibility of agricultural extension services and farm productivity The relationship between farmers' access to agricultural extension services and farm productivity was analyzed using the Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (see Table 7). This was initially formulated as a null hypothesis: The level of accessibility to agricultural extension services does not significantly improve farm productivity in the study area. Farmers' accessibility was measured in percentage terms, revealing that a significant portion (44.44%) had moderate access, while approximately 86.24% had a reasonable level of access to agricultural extension services. Farmers' level of accessibility to extension services showed a positive relationship with farm

productivity, indicating that increased access to extension services leads to higher productivity. The analytical technique employed assessed the statistical significance of variable X (farmers' access to extension services) in relation to variable Y (farm productivity), demonstrating the impact of extension services on agricultural output. The results indicated that the parameter estimate for variable X (farmers' access to extension services) was 0.6912, with a standard error (SE) of 0.2217. Half of the parameter estimate (0.3456), calculated as $0.6912 \div 2$, was greater than the standard error (0.2217). This finding suggests a statistically significant relationship between farmers' access to extension services (variable X) and farm productivity (variable Y). The Product Moment

Correlation Coefficient (r) was found to be 0.7452, indicating a strong positive and linear relationship between farmers' access to extension services (variable X) and farm productivity (variable Y). This positive correlation suggests that increased access to extension services leads to higher farm productivity. Based on these results, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative, confirming that the level of accessibility to agricultural extension services significantly enhances farm productivity in the study area. These

findings align with the conclusion of Ranjan *et al.* (2024), which emphasized that agricultural extension services play a crucial role in strengthening food security. They asserted that greater access to these services leads to increased food security through higher productivity. Furthermore, they highlighted that extension services serve as a bridge between research institutions and farmers, facilitating the transfer of knowledge, skills, and technologies to enhance agricultural productivity, sustainability, and resilience.

Table 7: Relationship between accessibility of agricultural extension services and farm productivity

Statistical variables	Parameter estimates
Parameter estimate of variable X	0.6912
Standard error of variable X	0.2217
'r' (Product Moment Correlation Coefficient)	0.7452
R2	0.6518
Half of the parameter estimate of variable X	0.3456

Source survey, Field survey, 2024

Relationship between level of farmers accessibility to extension services and food security The variation in farmers' access to extension services concerning food security is presented in Table 8, corresponding to Hypothesis 2, which states: There is no significant difference in food security levels between farmers with access to extension services and those without. This hypothesis was tested using the Binomial test statistics with the propensity score matching method (Logit). The outcome variable (Y) represents food security, which is influenced by the level of farmers' access to extension services. The results indicated that the majority of farmers (75.40%) had access to extension agents who provided them with agricultural extension services. This access increases their exposure to new innovations, technologies, and up-to-date agricultural information, ultimately enhancing productivity and food security. Conversely,

24.60% of farmers lacked access to extension services. The distribution of accessibility was skewed toward farmers with access to these services. The analysis showed statistical significance at the 1% level, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in favour of the alternative. This confirms that there is a significant difference in food security levels between farmers with access to extension services and those without. The level of farmers' accessibility to extension services may be attributed to the dedication of extension agents and the efforts of the Ministries of Agriculture, which are responsible for reaching out to farmers. This finding aligns with the study by Ikoyo-Eweto *et al.* (2023), who also observed a high level of farmers' access to extension services. They noted that such access is crucial for keeping farmers informed about current trends in improved agricultural technologies, which can enhance farm productivity and contribute to food security

Table 8: Level of farmers accessibility to extension services and food security

Variables	Category	N	Observed proportion	Test Proportion	Chi-square	Prob. Level
Farmers with access to extension services	Farmers with access (score: > 18)	285	0.754	0.50	358.0	0.000
	Farmers without access (score: 18 and below)	93	0.246			
	Total	378	1.000			

Significant at the 1% level

Source: Field survey, 2024

CONCLUSION

This study underscores the vital role of agricultural extension services in enhancing food security and farm productivity in Kaduna and Kano States. Notably, 86.24% of farmers had reasonable access to these services, with 44.44% enjoying moderate access. Key factors influencing accessibility included socio-economic characteristics, extension agent availability, farm organization membership, financial resources, capacity-building training, and ICT access. Extension agents played a pivotal role in disseminating agricultural information, providing technical advice, and facilitating access to inputs and credit. Consequently, farmers with better access to extension services experienced significant benefits, including: year-round food availability (76.98%), increased income (72.49%), higher crop yields (66.40%), improved technology adoption (61.64%), and reduced post-harvest losses (57.94%).

However, inadequate funding (92.86%) and poor logistics (91.01%) in addition to many other challenges, significantly hindered extension service effectiveness. These findings align with previous research, highlighting funding constraints and transportation difficulties as critical barriers. The study revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between access to extension services and farm

productivity (1% level). The results affirm that accessibility to agricultural extension services significantly enhances farm productivity and food security.

Based on the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

- There is a need for stake holders like government to increase the allocation in funding of Agricultural Ministries in general and Agricultural Extension unit in particular. This will help to support the extension service delivery system, ensuring that agents are well-equipped and trained to become more equipped for the job.
- Improve logistics by the government is also important in improving extension services to farmers. Such will enhance transportation infrastructure and provide necessary equipment to facilitate extension agents' mobility and outreach.
- Extension agents and farmers should be trained on latest farm technology and this should be carried out as a strategy of empowering them with more farm knowledge, that is capacity-building, and access to credit and inputs that will improve productivity and food security, and;
- A promotion of ICT-Based Extension Services is necessary for farmers to easily access information from. Doing this will go a long way to improve extension service access by farmers.

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